

EFFECT OF DELTAMETHRIN ON SOME ASPECTS OF LIPID METABOLISM IN FRESH WATER FISH *LABEO ROHITA* (HAMILTON)

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Received for publication: March 07, 2014; Revised: April 11, 2014; Accepted: April 21, 2014

Abstract: Effect of sub lethal concentration of deltamethrin (0.01µg/lit) was studied on total lipids, lipase activity and free fatty acids of the fish *Labeo rohita*. The levels of total lipids declined on 1st day exposure and gradually elevated on 7th day and 15th day. From 15th day onwards their levels gradually declined and came nearer to control at 30th day exposure period. In contrast to this the levels of lipase activity and free fatty acids followed an opposite trend.

Key Words: Deltamethrin, sublethal, *Labeo rohita*, total lipids, lipase activity and free fatty acids.

INTRODUCTION

In order to meet the global demand for increased food production a multitude fertilizers, chemicals and pesticides were put into use in ever increasing quantities. Pesticides are the biological toxicants which are required by man to kill insects, pests and also man's fight against the spread of diseases¹. As the use of these pesticides to control the crop destroying insects and also to control the spread of disease increase, so did the insect resistance to the pesticides and this led to synthesis of more new, more powerful and more toxic chemicals.

Pesticides usage became an indispensable and integral part of world agriculture. In addition to agriculture practices together with pest control programmes, the surface runoff and aerial spraying forming the major source for trans locating pesticides into aquatic ecosystems^{2,3,4}. Pesticides residues have been reported in fruits and vegetables^{5,6} and even in breast milk⁷. The contamination of water by pesticides may effect on non - target organisms like fish^{8,9,10}. So an attempt was made on sublethal effect of deltamethrin on some aspects of lipid metabolism in the fish *Labeo rohita*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Test Chemical

The pesticide selected for the present investigation was synthetic pyrethroid Deltamethrin. It is widely used on diverse agricultural crops to control pests of crops, flies and mosquitoes. It has been widely used because of its high photostability, degradability, non-persistent nature and low mammalian toxicity. Its commercial name was Decis. Commercial grade was used and its effective concentration was 2.8%.

Experimental design

Fresh water fish *Labeo rohita*, weighing 10±2gm were procured from local fisheries department and stored in spacious aquaria. The water in aquaria was aerated twice day, the fish were fed daily with groundnut cake and rice bran. The physico-chemical properties of water used for experiments had pH 7.4±0.2, dissolved oxygen 6-7 ml/lit, hardness 160 ppm and temperature 28±1 °C. Before experimentation has been executed, the fish were acclimated to the laboratory conditions for a period of 10 days. Later groups of 10 fish were exposed to different concentration of Deltamethrin ranging from 0.02µl to 0.2µl. The mortality was observed during 96 hrs exposure period. The LC₅₀ / 96 hrs was determined from the percent and probit mortality versus log concentration curves (Finney¹¹) and were subsequently verified by Dragstedt and Behrens method as given by Carpenter¹². After determination of LC₅₀/96 hrs (0.01µg/lit), the fish were exposed to sublethal concentration of Deltamethrin (1/10th of LC₅₀/96hrs i.e. 0.01 µg/lit) for five exposure periods i.e 1,7,15,20 and 30 day.

In the present investigation the levels of total lipids, lipase activity and free fatty acids were estimated in the brain, liver, gill, kidney and muscle of fish. Each experiment was carried out in the organs of six individuals and the mean of six values were taken into consideration. The total lipids were estimated by method of Folch et al.,¹³ lipase activity by Colowick and Caplan¹⁴ and free fatty acids by the method of Natelson¹⁵.

RESULTS

In this investigation the levels of total lipids, lipase activity and free fatty acids were estimated in the brain, liver, gill, kidney and muscle of fish, on

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1,7,15,20 and 30 days of exposure to sub lethal concentration of Deltamethrin besides control levels were presented in tables 1,2 and 3. The levels of total lipids declined relative to controls in all organs of fish at first day exposure and gradually elevated on 7 and 15 day exposure periods. From 15 day onwards their levels gradually declined and came nearer to control at 30 day exposure period. The values were found to be significant (P<0.001).

Table 1: Total lipids (mg/gm wet wt.) in the organs of *Labeo rohita* on exposure to sub lethal concentration of Deltamethrin. Mean and standard deviation are a pool of six individual measurements. The percent change in the total lipids at different periods was calculated in relation to the total lipids in the control medium. The differences between control and exposure period days were found to be statistically significant (P < 0.01).

S. No	Organs	Control	Exposure period in days				
			1 day	7 day	15 day	20 day	30 day
1.	Brain	82.0	60.5	68.2	72.4	63.5	59.5
	SD	4.0	2.02	3.72	2.42	3.14	3.15
	PC		-26.21	-16.82	-11.70	-22.56	-27.43
2.	Gill	58.6	32.2	41.5	47.6	42.5	39.0
	SD	3.02	1.72	2.07	2.56	1.90	1.56
	PC		-45.05	-29.18	-18.77	-27.47	-33.44
3.	Kidney	84.59	94.83	98.10	105.38	92.85	78.36
	SD	3.66	4.89	3.53	2.13	6.17	2.21
	PC		-12.10	-15.97	-24.57	-9.76	-7.36
4.	Liver	71.0	64.0	72.4	78.5	74.80	68.2
	SD	2.31	3.14	2.42	1.92	2.72	3.72
	PC		-9.85	-1.97	-10.56	-5.32	-3.94
5.	Muscle	23.0	18.7	24.0	29.5	25.2	21.5
	SD	1.98	2.18	3.39	2.11	3.70	2.78
	PC		-18.69	-4.34	-28.26	-11.30	-6.52

SD – Standard Deviation; PC – Percent change

Table 2: Lipase activity (mg/gm wet wt.) in the organs of *Labeo rohita* on exposure to sublethal concentration of Deltamethrin. Mean and standard deviation are a pool of six individual measurements. The percent change in the lipase activity at different periods was calculated in relation to the lipase activity in the control medium. The difference between control and exposure period days were found to be statistically significant (P < 0.01).

S. No	Organs	Control	Exposure period in days				
			1 day	7 day	15 day	20 day	30 day
1.	Brain	164.5	181.2	166.0	147.6	151.3	156.8
	SD	7.38	8.12	7.42	6.01	6.78	7.01
	PC		10.15	0.91	-10.27	-8.0	-4.68
2.	Gill	168.5	168.5	163.5	138.2	143.8	150.6
	SD	6.87	7.8	7.18	5.75	5.97	6.18
	PC		8.01	4.80	-11.41	-7.8	-3.46
3.	Kidney	132.5	156.0	151.1	143.6	136.5	125.4
	SD	8.25	9.75	8.72	7.30	7.95	8.10
	PC		17.73	14.49	8.37	-3.01	-5.35
4.	Liver	340.5	361.2	348.0	326.5	318.6	306.0
	SD	9.01	6.32	5.09	4.28	4.12	4.72
	PC		6.07	2.20	-4.11	-6.43	-10.13
5.	Muscle	81.2	104.0	96.5	66.8	71.2	77.0
	SD	3.64	4.18	4.10	2.78	3.01	3.30
	PC		-28.07	17.39	-18.13	-13.38	-6.32

SD – Standard Deviation; PC – Percent change

Table 3: Free fatty acids (mg/gm wet wt.) in the organs of *Labeo rohita* on exposure to sub lethal concentration of Deltamethrin. Mean and standard deviation are a pool of six individual measurements. The percent change in the free fatty acids at different periods was calculated in relation to the free fatty acids in the control medium. The differences between control and exposure period days were found to be statistically significant (P < 0.01).

S. No	Organs	Control	Exposure period in days				
			1 day	7 day	15 day	20 day	30 day
1.	Brain	6.62	6.98	6.46	5.86	6.26	6.48
	SD	0.68	0.72	0.79	0.52	0.62	.72
	PC		5.43	-2.41	-114.8	-5.43	-2.11
2.	Gill	2.13	2.14	1.92	1.68	1.85	2.12
	SD	2.12	2.42	1.92	1.40	2.01	2.59
	PC		13.14	-9.85	-21.12	-13.14	-0.46
3.	Kidney	8.46	8.59	8.42	8.22	8.82	8.12
	SD	1.23	1.87	1.50	1.24	1.70	1.62
	PC		3.58	-2.43	-2.54	-2.80	-6.01
4.	Liver	5.26	5.63	5.14	4.70	4.98	5.20
	SD	0.32	0.92	0.16	1.80	1.62	1.78
	PC		7.03	-2.28	-10.64	-5.32	-1.14
5.	Muscle	1.12	1.26	1.06	0.74	0.89	1.02
	SD	1.01	0.82	0.67	0.52	.071	0.92
	PC		12.50	-5.35	-33.92	-20.53	-8.92

SD – Standard Deviation; PC – Percent change

Whereas the levels of lipase activity and free fatty acids elevated in all organs of fish at first day exposure period, relative to controls. Their levels gradually declined on 7 and 15 day exposure periods. From 15 day onwards their levels gradually elevated and came nearer to control on 30 day exposure period. The values were found to be significant (P<0.001).

DISCUSSION

Lipids are heterogeneous group of complex macro molecules. They are the components of living system, insoluble in water but soluble in polar solvents. They form energy rich reserves whose calorific values are twice that of carbohydrates or proteins. The mobilization lipid reserve in an organism testifies the imposition of high energy demands¹⁶. Observations on the involvement of lipid metabolism exposed to pesticides are many¹⁷⁻²¹. All these studies shows that shifts in lipid metabolism when animals are exposed to toxicants.

The present study result also indicates the involvement of lipid metabolism in the fish *Labeo rohita* on exposure to sub lethal concentration of Deltamethrin. In this study relative to controls the levels of total lipids declined, whereas the levels of lipase activity and free fatty acids elevated on first day exposure. The decline in total lipid levels followed by elevation in the levels of lipase activity and free fatty acids on first day exposure indicates the high energy demand associated with imposed Deltamethrin stress. To overcome this animal tends to mobilize the lipids by stimulating the lipase activity. Some of the observations were also supports the present trend in

the decline of total lipid levels. Susan *et al.*,²² reported decrease in total lipid content when *Catla catla* exposed to pyrethroid, fenvalerate. Senthilkumar *et al.*,²³ found the reduction of lipid content in the freshwater crab *Spiralathelphusa hydrodroma* when it was exposed to a pesticide, chlorpyrifos. Frontera *et al.*,²⁴ observed decline in lipid content in hepatopancreas of freshwater crayfish *Cherax quadricarinatus* on exposure to glyphosate. Arun kumar and Jawahar Ali²⁵ reported similar decrease in lipid content in the fresh water shrimp *Streptocephalus dichotomus* on exposure to organophosphorus pesticides. Suneel kumar²⁶ reported significant decrease in total lipids in *Channa punctatus* on exposure to lethal concentration of nuvan.

Lipase activity initially elevated on 1 day exposure followed by its inhibition on 7 & 15 day exposure periods. This is clearly evident by drastic decline in free fatty acids and elevation in total lipids up to 15 day exposure period. Thus maximum percent inhibition in lipase activity and free fatty acids were seen at 15 day exposure period²⁷⁻³⁰. Swami *et al.*,¹⁸ observed metabolic shift from carbohydrate to lipid metabolism through acetyl-CoA barrier leading to an increment in lipids in the organs of fresh water mussel *Lamellidens marginalis* under pesticide toxicity. Similar significant decline in total lipids followed by elevation of lipase activity and free fatty acids has been reported in tissues of *Labeo rohita* exposed to sublethal concentration of Nuvan³¹. Furthermore Sirohi and Saxena³² also reported decreased in total lipids during initial exposure periods and gradually recovered on 30th day exposure period in fresh water fish *Channa Punctatus* on exposure to synthetic pyrethroid λ -Cyhalothrin.

In later half of exposure period the lipase activity and free fatty acid levels goes on elevation and came nearer to control on 30 day exposure period, whereas the levels of total lipids followed an opposite trend. Metabolic compensation involves break down and synthesis of products necessary to cope up with altered situations. In conclusion the shifts in lipid metabolism may be to compensate with altered situation shown by the fish for its survival.

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Source of support: Nil

Conflict of interest: None Declared